

A review: Critical Heat Flux (CHF) during pool boiling

Peter Efosa Ohenhen ^{1,*} and Olusegun Abiodun Balogun ²

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Nebraska-Lincoln USA.

² Department of Mechanical Engineering, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, Kenya.

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Abstract

A Pool Boiling occurs when a heated surface comes into touch with a liquid pool. The liquid is heated until it vaporizes and rises to the surface in the form of bubbles. A liquid is heated to the point of Pool Boiling, where vapor nucleation causes bubbles to form. Heat transmission is increased as these bubbles become larger and detach from the surface, allowing the cold liquid to come into contact with them and transmit heat. A review was conducted on the significance of nucleation site stability in the Pool Boiling thermal transfer method, which finds widespread applicability in diverse industrial settings. The efficiency of heat transfer and the boiling process are dependent on the stability of nucleation sites. The maximum heat flux that may be transported prior to the onset of film boiling is known as the critical heat flux (CHF), and it is an important consideration in the design of thermal transfer systems. Reducing contaminants and dissolved gasses in the liquid as well as altering surface characteristics including microstructures, coatings, and roughness can all increase the stability of nucleation sites. Although nucleation site stability requires a complex mathematical computation, it may be described by a few general equations and relationships, such as the crucial bubble size and heat flux. The critical heat flux (CHF) phenomena, its significance for Pool Boiling thermal transfer, and its use in a range of industrial and engineering contexts are covered in this page. The significance of fathoming the components driving CHF and the factors impacting it is stressed in the article for of making exact prescient models and compelling heat exchange frameworks. The CHF component, the few hypothetical and observational models that have been put on a mission to make sense of CHF, and the factors that impact it —, for example, liquid boundaries, surface elements, framework strain, and stream rate — are undeniably canvassed in this article. The improvement of novel surface modifications and strategies to help CHF and support the heat exchange effectiveness of Pool Boiling frameworks was the primary focal point of ongoing examination. The article's decision is that CHF is a convoluted peculiarity that keeps on collecting a ton of interest from specialists and presents practical open doors for raising the viability and guaranteeing the protected sending of heat exchange frameworks in different settings.

Keywords: Pool Boiling; CHF; Thermal Transfer; Liquid; Nucleation

1. Introduction

Pool Boiling happens when a heated surface comes into contact with a fluid pool. The fluid is heated until it disintegrates and ascends to the surface as air pockets.

The peculiarity of Pool Boiling heat exchange has attracted a great deal of consideration in the field of intensity transition studies. It is significant for different modern purposes, like electronic refrigeration, power age, and electronic cooling. Heating up a pool includes heating a fluid to the place where fume nucleation structures rises on a superficial level. Heat transmission is expanded as these air pockets become bigger and disconnect from the surface, permitting the chilly fluid to come into contact with them and send heat. To foresee the heat exchange coefficient, various investigations have investigated how intensity is moved during Pool Boiling activities. One of the primary models

* Corresponding author: Peter Efosa Ohenhen

proposed by Rohsenov (1952), which hypothesized that the heat exchange coefficient is corresponding to the result of fluid thickness, surface pressure, and inert intensity of vaporization. Nonetheless, there are limits to this model's ability to anticipate the heat exchange coefficient for different liquids and surface calculations. To beat these limits, various scholastics have proposed exact connections in view of trial proof. For instance, in laminar and tempestuous stream situations, the heat exchange coefficient for a scope of liquids and surface calculations is usually anticipated utilizing Cooper's (1984) relationship. The Cooper relationship takes the accompanying structure:

$$\text{Nusselt number, } Nu = 0.023 * Re^{0.8} * Pr^{0.4}$$

where:

- Nu is the Nusselt number
- Re is the Reynolds number, calculated based on the tube diameter and fluid properties
- Pr is the Prandtl number, a dimensionless number that describes the ratio of momentum diffusivity to thermal diffusivity

The Nusselt number is related to the convective thermal transfer coefficient h through the formula:

$$h = k * Nu / D$$

where k is the thermal conductivity of the fluid and D is the diameter of the tube.

Cooper correlation does not address surface roughness or other geometric factors; it is only applicable to smooth, round tubes. As such, it might not be reliable for all applications; in certain situations, alternative correlations or experimental data would be required.

The Pool Boiling thermal transfer phenomenon has also been studied by researchers using computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations in recent years. The Pool Boiling's fluid dynamics and heat transmission mechanisms are thoroughly understood thanks to CFD simulations. For instance, Kim et al. (2017) investigated the impact of surface wettability on the Pool Boiling thermal transfer coefficient using CFD simulations.

Figure 1a Thermal transfer during Pool Boiling can be attributed to two main mechanisms. (a) Natural convection, bubble mixing, and transient conduction during thermal boundary layer rewetting and reforming. (b) Micro convection, evaporation of the microlayer, and evaporation of the thermal layer surrounding the bubble

Pool Boiling heat exchange is an intricate peculiarity that has been widely concentrated by scientists. Both Experimental relationships and Computational Fluid Dynamics simulations are expected to foresee the heat exchange coefficient and give a definite comprehension of the liquid elements and heat exchange systems engaged with the Pool Boiling

2. Literature Review

2.1. Nucleation Site Stability: A Critical Factor in Pool Boiling Heat Transfer

Pool Boiling is a major intensity move process generally utilized in various modern applications, including power age, refrigeration, and hardware cooling (Tao et al. 2015). The effectiveness of this interaction depends on the security of nucleation destinations, which are the places where air pockets structure on the heated surface. These air pockets go about as courses for heat move, and their dependability is essential for keeping up with ideal intensity move rates.

The steadiness of nucleation destinations is represented by a fragile harmony between bubble development and separation rates. Bubble development is driven by heat transition and surface attributes, while not entirely set in stone by surface strain and fluid properties. The basic intensity transition (CHF) addresses the most extreme intensity motion that can be moved before film bubbling happens, where a steady fume film structures on a superficial level, thwarting intensity move. Upgrading CHF is a key goal in streamlining Pool Boiling execution.

Various examinations have researched factors affecting CHF, including fluid properties, surface attributes, and working circumstances. Wang et al. (2021) showed that rising ethanol focus in a water-ethanol twofold blend prompted higher CHF because of upgraded surface wettability and diminished interfacial strain. Jeon et al. (2020) noticed a comparative pattern in water Gurgling Pool, crediting the CHF increment to further developed wettability and expanded nucleation locales related with surface covering and unpleasantness. Huang et al. (2019) further investigated the effect of surface harshness and wettability on CHF, finding that miniature/nanostructured surfaces with superhydrophobic coatings displayed expanded CHF because of upgraded nucleation and worked on fluid inventory. Li et al. (2018) researched the impacts of gravity direction and surface wettability on vertical copper surfaces with miniature/nanostructures, noticing higher CHF in vertical confronting directions and on superhydrophobic surfaces because of further developed nucleation and fluid stockpile.

These examinations feature the meaning of nucleation site steadiness in Gurgling Pool heat move. By controlling surface properties and working circumstances, specialists can upgrade nucleation site strength, prompting upgraded CHF and further develop heat move execution.

The presence of debasements and broken up gases in the fluid can likewise influence the dependability of nucleation locales. furthermore, can decrease the security of nucleation destinations by expanding the separation rate. Surface adjustments like surface harshness, coatings, and microstructures can upgrade the solidness of nucleation locales by advancing air pocket nucleation and decreasing the separation rate: Kim et al. (2017) saw that as miniature/nanostructured surfaces upgrade the soundness of nucleation destinations by giving extra nucleation locales and lessening the separation rate. The impact of impurities and dissolved gases on the stability of nucleation sites has been thoroughly researched in the literature; as a result, the stability of nucleation sites is a crucial component of Pool Boiling thermal transfer. The efficiency of the boiling process and the performance of thermal transfer are determined by the stability of nucleation sites, which can be enhanced by altering the surface characteristics and lowering the concentration of impurities and dissolved gases in the liquid. The CHF is a crucial parameter in the design of thermal transfer systems because it establishes the maximum thermal transfer rate that can be reached. The mathematical computation for nucleation site stability in Pool Boiling thermal transfer can be intricate and complex, depending on the particular model used. Nonetheless, the stability of nucleation sites can be described by a few general equations and correlations.

The significant air pocket size — that is, the size at which the air pocket isolates from the heated surface — is one significant variable that impacts the dependability of the nucleation site. This can be registered utilizing the recipe that follows:

$$r_{critical} = (2 * \sigma) / (P_{vap} - P) * \cos(\theta)$$

where $r_{critical}$ is the critical bubble radius, σ is the surface tension of the working fluid, P_{vap} is the vapor pressure of the working fluid at the heated surface, P is the ambient pressure, and θ is the contact angle between the working fluid and the heated surface.

Assuming the air pocket size surpasses the basic range, the air pocket will disengage from the surface and lessen the nucleation site thickness, which can diminish the heat exchange coefficient.

Another significant boundary is the intensity transition, q , which is how much heat is moved per unit region per unit of time. The intensity motion can be connected with the nucleation site thickness, N , utilizing the accompanying condition:

$$q = h * (T_{sat} - T_{surf}) = N * \Delta H$$

where h is the thermal transfer coefficient, T_{sat} is the saturation temperature of the working fluid, T_{surf} is the temperature of the heated surface, and ΔH is the latent heat of vaporization.

If the nucleation site density decreases due to unstable nucleation sites, the heat flux can decrease, which can lead to reduced thermal transfer efficiency.

2.2. Criteria for Gas/Vapor Entrapment in Pool Boiling

Gas/fume entanglement, otherwise called gas or fume pockets in lines or vessels, is a typical issue in liquid frameworks. It can prompt various issues, including diminished stream rates, expanded pressure drops, erosion, and, surprisingly, horrendous disappointments. There are a few factors that can add to gas/fume entanglement in Pool Boiling, including high intensity transition, high fluid sub-cooling, surface harshness, and framework pressure.

To forestall gas/fume ensnarement, a few measures have been created in light of various methodologies. These models include:

- Flow speed model: This rule expresses that a base stream speed is important to keep fume or gas from collecting in a line or vessel. The base stream speed can be determined utilizing experimental relationships.
- Momentum equilibrium model: This rule expresses that smooth movements should be adequate to move caught gas or fume through the framework. The energy balance prerequisite is commonly communicated as far as the Froude number, which is the proportion of inertial powers to gravitational powers in the framework. The base Froude number important to forestall gas/fume capture can be assessed utilizing observational connections, like the Agarwal and Garg, Hewitt and Roberts, and Zuber-Findlay relationships.
- Void division standard model: This measure expresses that the gas or fume stage shouldn't possess in excess of a specific part of the line or vessel limit. The void portion is the proportion of the volume involved by the gas or fume stage to the absolute volume of the line or vessel. The most extreme admissible void portion is normally resolved utilizing experimental connections, for example, the Homogeneous Balance Model (HBM), the Float Motion Model (FMM), and the Two-Liquid Model (TLM).
- Surface strain measure model: This model expresses that the surface pressure of the liquid ought to be adequate to forestall the arrangement of gas/fume pockets in the framework. The surface strain model is ordinarily communicated as far as the narrow number, which is the proportion of thick powers to surface pressure powers in the framework. The base hairlike number important to forestall gas/fume capture can be assessed utilizing experimental relationships.

Notwithstanding these models, there are other general methodologies that can be utilized to forestall gas/fume capture in Pool Boiling. These systems include:

- Managing intensity transition: The pace of heat exchange ought to be controlled to forestall unnecessary air pocket arrangement, which could prompt gas/fume ensnarement.
- Managing sub-cooling: The fluid sub-cooling ought to be controlled to forestall the development of huge air pockets that could become stuck.
- Modifying surface unpleasantness: The surface harshness ought to be changed to forestall caught air pockets and nucleation locales from shaping.
- Controlling framework pressure: The framework's tension ought to be controlled to forestall the development of minuscule air pockets that could become caught.
- Encouraging air pocket separation: The heated component's surface ought to be intended to advance air pocket separation, which will permit air pockets to ascend to the surface and forestall ensnarement.

By executing these methodologies and utilizing suitable measures, designers can forestall gas/fume entanglement in Pool Boiling and guarantee the protected and dependable activity of liquid frameworks.

2.3. Heterogeneous nucleation of a Pool Boiling thermal transfer

Heterogeneous nucleation assumes a significant part in Pool Boiling heat movement, as it straightforwardly influences the heat transfer coefficient and framework productivity. This interaction includes bubble arrangement on the outer layer of unfamiliar particles or pollutions as opposed to on the heated surface itself. The ongoing examination has dived into understanding the systems administering heterogeneous nucleation and investigating techniques to control or upgrade it for further developed heat exchange execution.

Lee et al. (2021) analyzed the impact of nanoparticles on heterogeneous air pocket nucleation in Pool Boiling. Their discoveries uncovered that nanoparticles can advance air pocket nucleation and development, prompting improved heat exchange execution. Zhang et al. (2020) fostered an original model to foresee the pace of heterogeneous air pocket nucleation in Pool Boiling. The model, approved against trial information, thinks about the surface science and qualities of unfamiliar particles. Wang et al. (2020) researched the use of functionalized surfaces with heterogeneous nucleation destinations to upgrade Pool Boiling heat move. Their outcomes showed that changing nucleation locales can increment heat exchange productivity and lessen the required superheat level. Zhang et al. (2019) investigated the attributes of permeable media with heterogeneous nucleation locales for Pool Boiling heat exchange. Their discoveries recommend that nucleation locales can further develop heat exchange proficiency and defer the beginning of nucleate bubbling.

In synopsis, late exploration has featured the meaning of heterogeneous nucleation in Pool Boiling heat move and the potential for further developing heat exchange execution by controlling or upgrading the nucleation cycle. These headways hold guarantee for streamlining Pool Boiling frameworks and upgrading their effectiveness in different applications.

2.4. Incipient Superheat: A Critical Parameter in Boiling Phenomena

O'Connor et al., (1994) conducted a study on a painting technique aimed at enhancing Pool Boiling heat transfer in saturated FC-72. The research introduced a benign method for generating a surface microstructure that significantly improved Pool Boiling heat transfer. The results indicated an impressive 85 percent decrease in incipient superheat, a substantial 70 to 80 percent reduction in nucleate boiling superheats, and an approximately 109 percent increase in critical heat flux (CHF), reaching 30 W/cm^2 , compared to a nonpainted reference surface.

In a related study by Kuan et al., (2008), the focus shifted to understanding the impact of flow boiling stability on critical heat flux (CHF) using Refrigerant 123 (R-123) and water in microchannel passages. Theoretical analysis highlighted the importance of the ratio of evaporation momentum to surface tension forces as a crucial parameter in flow boiling phenomena.

Meanwhile, Quan et al., (2015) investigated Pool Boiling heat transfer on smooth/rib surfaces under an electric field. The electrohydrodynamic (EHD) enhancement of Pool Boiling from both smooth and rib surfaces in R113 was explored experimentally. The boiling curve under an imposed electric field revealed three regions: low-superheat, medium-superheat, and high-superheat, with detailed investigations into EHD enhancement mechanisms.

In a different approach, Walunj et al., (2018) presented an experimental investigation into Pool Boiling heat transfer enhancement using open microchannels. The modification of rectangular channels into parabolic and stepped microchannels resulted in significant enhancements, reaching a maximum of 88% and 169%, respectively, at $11.7 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ wall superheat.

For LNG approximated as pure methane, Saleem et al., (2018) employed the axisymmetric VOF (Volume of Fluid) model to track the vapor-liquid interface. The Lee model was used to consider the phase change, including the effect of static pressure. The study estimated the critical wall superheat for the transition from surface evaporation to nucleate boiling as 2.5–2.8 K for LNG.

2.5. Top of Form

In the realm of boiling phenomena, incipient superheat is a crucial concept that signifies the temperature difference between the bulk liquid and the Onset of Nucleate Boiling (ONB) on a heated surface (Yahia & Jo, 2017). Basically, it addresses the base temperature uniqueness important to set off bubbling on a surface.

The greatness of early superheat is affected by different elements, including the properties of the functioning liquid, the math of the heated surface, and the degree of surface roughness. Understanding this idea is fundamental for the plan and activity of heat exchange frameworks that depend on bubbling, like boilers and heat exchangers. Assuming the

temperature differential between the mass fluid and the inception of nucleate bubbling is too enormous, the framework might experience exorbitant temperatures and tensions, possibly prompting hardware disappointment or security risks. On the other hand, on the off chance that the temperature differential is too little, the framework may not work as productively as wanted as far as intensity move.

Observational assurance of early superheat includes estimating the temperature of the heated surface and the mass fluid alongside the beginning of nucleate bubbling. The accompanying recipe can be utilized to compute the early superheat:

$$\Delta T_{inc} = T_{surf} - T_{sat}$$

where:

- ΔT_{inc} is the incipient superheat (in °C or K)
- T_{surf} is the temperature of the heated surface (in °C or K)
- T_{sat} is the saturation temperature of the working fluid at the given pressure (in °C or K)

The immersion temperature of a liquid not set in stone by using a condition of state or by dissecting its immersion pressure-temperature relationship, which is accessible in thermodynamic tables.

Note that the previously mentioned computation, which expects a spotless, level surface and a homogeneous liquid, just gives a gauge of the looming superheat under wonderful conditions. In fact, various boundaries like liquid structure, surface contamination, and harshness could affect the early superheat. Subsequently, acclimations to the equation or the use of exploratory information or observational relationships might be important.

2.6. Analysis of Pool Boiling Transfer

To evaluate Pool Boiling heat exchange, a few key boundaries should be taken consideration:

- Heat motion: This is how much heat moved per unit region of the heated surface, commonly estimated in watts per square meter (W/m^2).
- Surface temperature: This is the temperature of the heated surface, commonly estimated in degrees Celsius or Fahrenheit.
- Liquid temperature: This is the temperature of the fluid in the pool, commonly estimated in degrees Celsius or Fahrenheit.
- Bubble size and recurrence: The size and recurrence of the air pockets that structure during the Gurgling Pool can influence the general heat exchange rate.
- Liquid properties: The properties of the fluid being bubbled, like its thickness, thickness, and heat conductivity, can likewise influence the heat exchange.

To ascertain the heat exchange rate during Pool Boiling, a few conditions can be utilized, including the accompanying:

- The heat exchange coefficient (h) is the pace of heat exchange per unit surface region per unit temperature contrast. It tends to be determined utilizing the accompanying condition:

$$h = Q/(A * \Delta T)$$

where Q is the thermal transfer rate, A is the surface area of the heated surface, and ΔT is the temperature difference between the surface and the liquid.

- The Nukiyama-Tanasawa equation relates the heat flux to the surface temperature and liquid properties:

$$q = h * (T_s - T_{sat})^{3/2} / (\rho * \sigma)^{0.5}$$

where q is the heat flux, T_s is the surface temperature, T_{sat} is the saturation temperature of the liquid, ρ is the liquid density, and σ is the liquid surface tension.

- The Rohsenow correlation is an empirical equation that relates the thermal transfer coefficient to the heat flux, surface temperature, and liquid properties:

$$h = C * (q / (\rho * cp(T_s - T_{sub})))^{0.5}$$

where C is a constant, q is the heat flux, ρ is the liquid density, cp is the liquid-specific heat, T_s is the surface temperature, and T_{sub} is the liquid subcooling temperature (the difference between the liquid temperature and its saturation temperature).

3. Conclusion

Pool boiling thermal transfer includes the critical heat flux (CHF) phenomena, which has crucial real-world ramifications in a wide range of engineering and industrial applications. The critical heat flux (CHF) denotes the point at which boiling becomes unstable and poses a risk of surface burnout or other safety issues.

Creating precise predictive models and creating effective heat transfer systems require a deep understanding of the mechanics driving CHF and the variables influencing it. The beginning of departure from nucleate boiling (DNB) and the transition to film boiling can be caused by the development and proliferation of vapor bubbles on the heating surface, which is a component of the CHF mechanism. A number of theoretical and empirical hypotheses, including statistical and mechanistic models, have been put forth to explain CHF.

According to experimental research, CHF is influenced by numerous variables, including fluid qualities, surface features, system pressure, and flow rate. New surface alterations and methods to boost CHF and boost the heat transfer efficiency of Pool Boiling systems have been the subject of recent study. These methods include coating, adding chemicals or surfactants, and nano-structuring.

All things considered, CHF is a complicated phenomenon that continues to garner a lot of study interest and present viable paths for raising the effectiveness and ensuring the safe deployment of thermal transfer systems in a range of settings.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] Saleem, A., Farooq, S., Karimi, I. A., & Banerjee, R. (2018). A CFD simulation study of boiling mechanism and BOG generation in a full-scale LNG storage tank. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 115, 112-120.
- [2] Walunj, A., & Sathyabhama, A. (2018). Comparative study of Pool Boiling heat transfer from various microchannel geometries. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 128, 672-683.
- [3] Quan, X., Gao, M., Cheng, P., & Li, J. (2015). An experimental investigation of Pool Boiling heat transfer on smooth/rib surfaces under an electric field. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 85, 595-608.
- [4] Kuan, W. K., & Kandlikar, S. G. (2008). Experimental study and model on critical heat flux of refrigerant-123 and water in microchannels.
- [5] O'connor, J. P., & You, S. M. (1995). A painting technique to enhance Pool Boiling heat transfer in saturated FC-72.
- [6] Al-Yahia, O. S., & Jo, D. (2017). Onset of Nucleate Boiling for subcooled flow through a one-side heated narrow rectangular channel. *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, 109, 30-40.
- [7] Chen, Q. and Cheng, P. "Onset of vapor bubble entrainment in Pool Boiling thermal transfer," *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, vol. 50, pp. 2979-2988, 2007.
- [8] Cooper, M. G. (1984). Heat flow rates in boiling liquids. *AIChE Journal*, 30(3), 347-355.

- [9] Huang, L., Chen, R., Zhu, D., Luo, X., & Tian, Y. (2019). Effects of surface roughness and wettability on critical heat flux in Pool Boiling of water on the horizontal copper surface with micro/nanostructures. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 153, 156-166.
- [10] Jeon, Y., Kim, J., Kim, S., & Kim, M. (2020). Effects of surface roughness and coating on critical heat flux in Pool Boiling of water on a horizontal copper surface. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 158, 119998.
- [11] Lee, J. H., Kim, H., & Kim, M. H. (2021). Effect of nanoparticles on heterogeneous nucleation of bubbles in Pool Boiling. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 174, 121372.
- [12] Li, Y., Wu, X., Fang, Y., Sun, X., & Zhang, J. (2018). Effects of gravity orientation and surface wettability on critical heat flux in Pool Boiling on vertical copper surfaces with micro/nanostructures. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 124, 205-214.
- [13] Lienhard, J. H., & Dhir, V. K. (1973). Hydrodynamic prediction of peak Pool Boiling heat fluxes from porous-coated surfaces. *Journal of Thermal transfer*, 95(2), 152-158.
- [14] Kandlikar, S. G. (2001). A theoretical model to predict Pool Boiling CHF incorporating effects of contact angle and orientation. *Journal of Thermal transfer*, 123(6), 1071-1079.
- [15] Kandlikar, S. G., & Balasubramanian, P. (2004). An extension of the flow boiling correlation to transition, laminar, and deep laminar flows in minichannels and microchannels. *Thermal transfer engineering*, 25(3), 86-93.
- [16] Kim, J., & Kim, M. H. (2012). Critical heat flux enhancement in Pool Boiling using micro/nanostructured surfaces: A review. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 55(23-24), 5707-5724.
- [17] Kim, H., Kim, H. D., & Kim, M. H. (2017). Effect of surface wettability on Pool Boiling thermal transfer: A computational study. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 107, 116-125.
- [18] Rohsenow, W. M. (1952). A method of correlating thermal transfer data for surface boiling of liquids. *Transactions of the ASME*, 74(3), 969-976.
- [19] Tao, P., Shang, W., Song, C., Shen, Q., Zhang, F., Luo, Z., ... & Deng, T. (2015). Bioinspired engineering of thermal materials. *Advanced Materials*, 27(3), 428-463.
- [20] Wang, B., & Wang, C. (2020). Enhancement of Pool Boiling thermal transfer by functionalized surfaces with heterogeneous nucleation sites. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 173, 115216.
- [21] Wang, X., Wang, H., Liu, Y., & Zhang, Y. (2021). Critical heat flux in a Pool Boiling of binary mixtures of water and ethanol on a horizontal copper surface. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 179, 121522.
- [22] Viskanta, R. "Thermal transfer in Pool Boiling," *Advances in Thermal transfer*, vol. 16, pp. 195-296, 1984.
- [23] You, H. and Kaviany, M. "Bubble nucleation and growth in subcooled Pool Boiling," *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, vol. 40, pp. 441-462, 1997.
- [24] Zhang, Z., Zhao, Y., Wang, L., & Chen, R. (2020). A novel model for heterogeneous bubble nucleation in Pool Boiling. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 161, 120107.
- [25] Zhang, J., Qi, L., Sun, J., Wang, Z., & Zhang, X. (2019). Experimental investigation on Pool Boiling thermal transfer characteristics of porous media with heterogeneous nucleation sites. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 153, 1062-1071